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PLATOON

Digital platform and analytic tools for energy

Deliverable D9.2 Website update, materials

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Abstract:	This document is a visual presentation of the PLATOON project website as well as other online and offline communication & dissemination tools. The website as well as other materials will be used to disseminate and communicate the project itself, its vision, mission, aims and project outcomes to relevant stakeholders.
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Terms and Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DM	Dissemination Manager
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
ESCO	Energy Service Company
GA	Grant Agreement
GAM	General Assembly Meeting
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
LI	LinkedIn
PM	Project Manager

PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
RE	Restricted
SC	Steering Committee
TM	Technical Manager
TSO	Transmission System Operator
TTP	Technology Transfer Programme
TW	Twitter
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WPL9	Leader of Work Package 9
YT	YouTube

Executive Summary

PLATOON is an EU-financed project that was launched in January 2020. It will research ways to digitalise the energy sector by developing COSMAG-compliant reference architecture for big data processing. The project partners will create a digital platform and multiple analytic tools – specifically for the energy sector – that will gather and summarise information from multiple sources (i.e. renewable energy power plants, ESCOs, end users, TSOs, DSOs, etc.), thus helping stakeholders to find and use effectively the most relevant and updated information when being active on the energy market.

The D9.2 “Website update, materials” is a deliverable of WP9 “Communication and Dissemination” to be delivered in Month 4 (M4). The main goal of WP9 is to promote and communicate the project widely at local, national and European level while engaging key stakeholders for knowledge sharing. The purpose of the current deliverable is to present the dissemination materials that were created and uploaded on the project website (both public and private areas), social media accounts as well as printed materials. A short description about each of these materials and their corresponding screenshots are included in the deliverable. The promotional materials are part of the project’s external communication and as such they will be updated regularly as the project progresses, highlighting its developments.

Chapter 1 is the introductory chapter of the current deliverable. It provides a general overview of the project, it presents the scope and the objectives of the deliverable and analyses the methodology used towards its realisation. Chapter 2 presents the PLATOON project website (<http://platoon-project.eu/>), which is designed, developed and operated by ENGIE and TIB. It is the major dissemination and information channel of the project; it includes all relevant information about the project and the dissemination materials as well. Chapter 3 includes the full list of the general dissemination materials that were produced for the internal and external promotion and marketing activities of the project, i.e. the project's logo, general presentation, the press release and the newsletter. Furthermore, a number of figures are included in this chapter, offering a visual presentation of the materials to the reader. In Chapter 4, a reference is made to the social media profiles that were created for the project (Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube). Chapter 5 discusses the printed materials such as the brochures, posters etc. Chapter 6 is an extra chapter referring to the current COVID-19 situation worldwide and the resulting consequences for the PLATOON project. Chapter 7 is dedicated to the conclusions highlighting the important role of the dissemination materials for the promotion of the project throughout its duration. Therefore, keeping them updated is essential in sharing the project's developments and progress with the partners and the general public and raising awareness and visibility. In Chapter 8, we included two internal reviews from our partners FBA and ENGIE and in Chapter 9 we included some references of our document.

1. Introduction

Deliverable 9.2 (Del 9.2) is part of WP9 “Communication and Dissemination” of the PLATOON project. It provides a comprehensive overview of the promotional materials and means that will be used for the dissemination of the PLATOON project. PLATOON is a three year project that was launched in January 2020 with the aim to assist several stakeholders such as energy companies, ESCOs, TSOs, DSOs, ICT companies as well as energy end users by developing a digital platform and energy-related tools to use a wide array of up-to-date energy data. Hereby, PLATOON will develop COSMAG-compliant reference architecture for big data processing specifically for the energy sector. Furthermore, the project will be validated in 7 pilots in 5 countries that provide real Energy Big Data cases. The project's main goals are:

- To enhance the role of the energy sector stakeholders to let them reliably, fairly and securely extract knowledge from their own data.
- To foster the new business models in the energy sector using digital technologies.
- To enhance multi-party cooperation between technology providers and data owners.
- To contribute to the standardisation of the energy management systems by assessing whether current standards offer the proper roles interfaces to enable business processes, including new ones and identify where new standards that may be needed, according to the COSMAG reference architecture.

By achieving these goals, PLATOON will contribute to the rise of the renewable energy sources shared within the energy sector, improve smart grids, increase energy efficiency of buildings, power plants, and vehicles as well as optimise energy asset management in various areas. Through close interaction with EU policy makers, the PLATOON project will reinforce the European efforts for the modernisation of the European electricity grid, as it focuses on new smart grids services through data knowledge exploitation. Finally, PLATOON will offer access to cheaper and sustainable energy for end users and maximise social welfare. PLATOON is a project funded by the EU under the GA No. 872592.

2. Website

The PLATOON website serves as the main tool for collection, exploitation and dissemination of project-related information. It is developed by ENGIE in close collaboration with TIB. The domain name of the website is <http://platoon-project.eu/>. The PLATOON website follows a web-responsive design and as such friendly URLs will be used.

The efficiency of PLATOON's website is underpinned by the criteria of:

- Usability, i.e. clear and accessible structure
- Content updating
- Accuracy in the content suitability
- Provision of relevant and current information to a wide audience
- Serving as an information database of all the activities and public deliverables implemented by the project and its partners related to the PLATOON project.

All partners will be requested to deliver content for the website, e.g. in the form of blog posts for the news sections and/ or by providing content for other website sections. The main objective in this case is that the latest status of the project is reflected on the website. The working language of the website is English. Nevertheless, effort will be made for major project updates which will be communicated as Press Releases, to be translated by the partners in the languages of the Consortium and featured as well on the project website, in the "Press" section.

The website map has been designed to offer a complete overview of the project and give easy access to all its activities. Moreover, there will be a main "News & Events" section promoting the latest updates related to PLATOON calls, events or activities open to the public. The download areas will be available per section, giving the possibility of free downloads of all the public outputs carried out during the project's life phase, including the brochures of the project, its media kit, public deliverables etc. The website will also allow visitors to formalise their online subscriptions to PLATOON events and to register for the project's newsletter.

As of now (M4), the following structure is proposed and implemented for the project’s website. Of course this structure can be further updated and adjusted during the project in order to serve best the project’s objectives.

TIB, as the Lead of WP9, will coordinate the consortium with respect to collecting input and updates from the consortium partners and updating accordingly the relevant website sections as well as the communication channels of the project.

2.1 Home

When visiting the PLATOON website, users are presented the homepage that is depicted from Figure 1 to 3. At the top of the page, a header includes a clear view of the PLATOON logo to promote its visual identity and a navigation bar where menu and submenu options lead to the respective pages. A clearer and more detailed view of the navigation structure can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 1: PLATOON Homepage (Part 1)

In the main panel, there is a short description of the general concept, the architecture, the challenges, the goals and the vision of the project. Next, a sample of recent news article blocks about PLATOON aims to forward the project’s activity, by triggering the interest of people into reading more. Further below, the members of the consortium are introduced in the form of their logos and a newsletter subscription space. By clicking on the logos of each partner, the viewer can be directed to their respective website. Two arrows are used left and right, in order to facilitate the navigation of the viewer as per the logos of 20 PLATOON partners.

Figure 2: PLATOON Homepage Part 2

Partners

Figure 3: PLATOON Homepage (Part 3)

Figure 4: PLATOON Website Navigation Bar

The main menu tabs includes the following nine subpages:

- Home

- About PLATOON
- News & Events
- Platform
- Pilots
- Resources
- Network
- Ethics & Security
- Contact

The proposed subsections of each of the subpages are presented from Chapter 2.2 to Chapter 2.8.

Additional elements

For all visitors that wish to submit questions or learn more about the PLATOON project the website's "Contact" tab provides all the necessary information in order to get in touch with the project team, along with a contact form for instant messaging.

Finally, at the bottom of every page there is a footer (Figure 3) that contains useful links to the project's Twitter (TW) page, LinkedIn (LI) company page and the YouTube (YT) channel. All of them are described more in detail in Chapter 4. Also, a "Sitemap" section, presenting all the subpages of the website as well as the most recent news titles and headlines are shown on the very bottom of the PLATOON homepage.

2.2 About PLATOON

On the "About PLATOON" the visitors can gain generic info regarding the PLATOON project, its main goals, its purpose, and its stakeholders. By clicking on the "More about PLATOON" button on the PLATOON Homepage, the users land on the "About PLATOON" subpage.

"About PLATOON" has the following subsections:

- 1- Overview

This is the site that the user automatically lands on by clicking either on "More about PLATOON" on the Homepage or on "About PLATOON" in the navigation bar. Here, a more detailed PLATOON project description is given, as well as an outlook on future outcomes, challenges, visions, and aims. In the centre of this subpage, a generic wind farm picture is shown, similarly as on the PLATOON Homepage to catch the viewers' attention. This picture can be enlarged, if the user wishes to do so.

Figure 5: About PLATOON subpage, Overview

The EU-funded H2020 project PLATOON aims to digitalise the energy sector, enabling thus higher levels of operational excellence with the adoption of disrupting technologies.

PLATOON will deploy distributed edge processing and data analytics technologies for optimized real-time energy system management in a simple way for the energy domain expert. The data governance among the different stakeholders for multi-party data exchange, coordination and cooperation in the energy value chain will be guaranteed via IDS based connectors. The project will develop and use the PLATOON reference architecture, which is COSMAG-compliant, for building and deploying scalable and replicable energy management solutions, contributing thus to increased renewable energy consumption, smart grids management, increased energy efficiency and optimised energy asset management, addressing the needs of various stakeholders along the value chain of the energy sector.

The project will be validated in 7 pilots in 5 countries that provide real Energy Big Data cases. PLATOON will facilitate the technology transfer into the market by a well-established tendering process via Open Calls.

PLATOON will reinforce the European efforts for the modernisation of the European electricity grid, as it focuses on new smart grids services through data knowledge exploitation. Moreover PLATOON will offer access to cheaper and sustainable energy for energy consumers and maximise social welfare.

Thus PLATOON will contribute to increased renewable energy consumption, smart grids management, increased energy efficiency and optimised energy asset management.

2- Scope and Objectives

Figure 6: About PLATOON subpage, Scope and Objectives section

PLATOON aims at achieving the following scientific and technological objectives:

Objective 1: To define and promote a COSMAG-compliant reference architecture.

Objective 2: To design and develop an open, vendor-independent data governance scheme based on IDS (International Data Space) principles which guarantees data sovereignty and privacy for all the stakeholders.

Objective 3: To develop a specific interoperability layer that enables heterogenous, bulky and high speed-data transfer from the pilots to the PLATOON platform.

Objective 4: To develop, deploy, integrate and validate a data analytics toolbox easy to be used by energy experts and customized to solve the specific needs of the energy infrastructures operators and data owners.

Objective 5: To design and implement local real time processing capabilities in the edge to provide local smartness and alleviate the data transfer to the PLATOON components deployed in the cloud.

This is the second section of the “About PLATOON” subpage. Here, the users get an idea what PLATOON’s main goals are and in how far the scope of the project covers the challenges within the energy sector. Also, the visitors get a detailed overview of the objectives that need to be met in order to achieve PLATOON’s global goals.

3- Approach

Figure 7: About PLATOON subpage, Approach section

In this section, the visitors receive information on how the PLATOON Consortium wants to achieve the aforementioned global goals. Here, we describe the concept and measures how the digital platform and analytical tools for the energy sector are created.

4- Impact

Figure 8: About PLATOON subpage, Impact section

Here, we describe more in detail how PLATOON will influence various areas within the energy sector as well as other energy-intensive businesses or industries that are permanently dealing with energy issues. Also, we will talk about how exactly the outcomes of the PLATOON project should benefit these industries. It also lists the anticipated socioeconomic effects.

5- Expected Results

Figure 9: About PLATOON subpage, Expected Results section

This section is about the expected outcomes that PLATOON is supposed to deliver by end of the project. Here, we focus on the future benefits that various stakeholders should gain from the results of the project.

6- Consortium Partners

Figure 10: About PLATOON subpage, Consortium Partners section

This section analyses the 20 PLATOON partners that take part in the project. We introduce all of them, and elaborate on the specific role of each of the partners and their contribution to the positive development of the project. To illustrate the PLATOON Consortium, we included a map that shows all nine countries that take part in the project and the location of the seven pilots as well as the full names of the PLATOON companies and institutions.

7- FAQ

Figure 11: About PLATOON subpage, FAQ section

In this section, we will answer the questions that website viewers as well as interested multidisciplinary stakeholders, could have regarding the PLATOON project. Hereby, the questions cover a broad spectrum ranging from generic ones to more specific ones and technical ones. For instance, the questions will cover community building aspects, e.g. how to become an associated partner of PLATOON or an ambassador etc. At the same time, useful information will be provided to address domain questions of the energy sector and the data science area, aiming thus to provide quality input for experts of different domains, interested in multidisciplinary research. Furthermore the FAQ section will explain certain keywords used within the context of the project, such as open calls, edge computing or smart grid infrastructure etc. Over time, we will analyse the questions that the website users, newsletter subscribers or other interested stakeholders address to the Communications partners, while regularly updating the FAQ throughout the project.

8- Press

Figure 12: About PLATOON subpage, Press section

The press section will include links to the press releases of the PLATOON project in English and other languages of the PLATOON Consortium. Moreover in this section, press clips will be added in which the PLATOON project is mentioned. The press contacts will be visibly added in this section, as well as in the contact section.

Moreover in this section, a **digital media kit** will be featured, which can easily be downloaded by interested media contacts. The media kit will contain resources and information for reporters and publishers, serving thus the objective to enable reporters to quickly learn about the project, and access photos and marketing materials they can use. More specifically, the PLATOON press kit will include:

- Generic press release of the PLATOON project, written in a compelling way and outlining core project information, e.g. the objectives of the project etc.
- The logo of the project in high resolution.
- Project factsheet.
- Other high-resolution photos and images which are relevant to the project.
- Media contacts.
- Canned quotes of and approved by the PLATOON Consortium that the media can use in their publications. This makes it easier for reporters to attribute direct quotes without having to reach out or coordinate an interview.
- Brochures, stickers and A4 posters in downloadable forms.

9- Dissemination Materials

Figure 13: About PLATOON subpage, Dissemination Materials section

This section describes the printed dissemination materials that the PLATOON Consortium uses in order to promote the project. This includes A1 and A4 posters, stickers, brochures, among others. These dissemination materials will be published as downloadable PDF-documents. More info on printed materials in Chapter 5.

10- Stakeholders

Figure 14: About PLATOON subpage, Stakeholders section

In the final section of “About PLATOON” we list all stakeholders that should benefit from the outcomes of the PLATOON project results. These are various groups such as ESCOs, TSOs, DSOs, and energy end users just to name a few. Here, we elaborate on how exactly they should profit from PLATOON and which tools would help them by achieving their areas of interest.

2.3 News & Events

The “News & Events” tab navigates to the blog-like page depicted in Figure 15, where visitors are able to find blog posts and articles that are linked to the project, published from most recent to oldest ones. The purpose of this category is not only to inform about the project’s progress, but also to attract stakeholders that could potentially be interested in the relevant research fields. In addition to this page, most recent news posts are also displayed

on the homepage (as it was mentioned in Section 2.1). “News and Events” has the following subsections:

1- News

This is the section where the users land whenever they click on the “News & Events” area in the navigation bar. Here, we display the more generic news about the PLATOON project. For instance, blog posts provided by the partners as per their communication activities pertaining to PLATOON, e.g. organisation of workshops, presentation of the PLATOON project in webinars, conferences and expositions. Furthermore, TIB will invite the PLATOON Consortium to write blog posts on other topics relevant to the project, and to share thus insights from research and lessons learned within these domains.

Figure 15: PLATOON News & Events subpage, News section

2- Press Releases

Figure 16: PLATOON News & Events subpage, Press Releases section

This category is created specifically for Press Release news, as a supplement to the regular news. Press Releases are of special importance and are therefore displayed both in the News and in the Press Release subsections.

3- Interviews

Figure 17: PLATOON News & Events subpage, Interviews section

In this section, the PLATOON partners are presenting themselves in the form of a short interview. The website visitors will thus have the opportunity to get to know the PLATOON partners, their views on the energy industry in general, their respective role in the PLATOON project and the value of the PLATOON project for the energy market. We also include a short CV as well as a photo of each interviewee so that the website users can get an idea who the people behind the PLATOON project are. This forms the interview campaign entitled “Meet the Consortium” and will be further disseminated via the social media accounts of the

project, aiming to increase the visibility of the project as well as the number of website visitors and views.

4- Open Calls

Figure 18: PLATOON News & Events subpage, Open Calls section

Open calls will be implemented in the context of the PLATOON project in order to engage the external community in the project's innovation activities and foster an innovative ecosystem around PLATOON. In this section, we describe more in detail how these open calls will be implemented.

The section will contain general information about the open calls that will be launched, indicating:

- Name of the open call.
- Objective.
- Launch and closing dates.
- Services and funding offered to participants.
- Eligibility criteria.

There will also be a link to a micro-site created on FundingBox platform, www.fundingbox.com, which will serve as an entry point to the application form. This micro-site will bring and complement the information of the project's website, mentioned above, adding rules and conditions, and more details about what is offered to the selected participants of each open call.

5- Webinars

Figure 19: PLATOON News & Events subpage, Webinars section

This section is about the webinars that TIB as the WPL9 will organise for both internal and external PLATOON stakeholders. Here, the visitors receive information on the topic of the webinars, the time when they will take place and further information, such as the links to the corresponding YouTube videos, as the live webinars will be then uploaded to the YouTube channel of the project.

6- Workshops and Conferences

Figure 20: PLATOON News & Events subpage, Workshops and Conferences section

In this last section of “News & Events”, we will publish the already completed and the upcoming workshops as well as the conferences in which the PLATOON partners will participate. The role of each conference attendee will be detailed and information will be shared as per these events and how PLATOON was promoted in this context (e.g. via presentation, booth etc.).

2.4 Platform

“Platform” has the following sections:

1- Description

Figure 21: PLATOON Platform subpage, Description section

Here, we present the cyber-secure digital energy platform that allows for large-scale multi-party data exchange, processing and monetisation, all governed by a clear data governance policy. One of the major objectives of PLATOON is the deployment and validation of a PLATOON platform, based on the defined reference architecture in each of the seven pilots. On this subpage, we explain the digital energy platform more in detail as well as the purpose and the areas of implementation. We also clarify how stakeholders can benefit from this platform.

2- Energy Big Data Analytics Tools

Figure 22: PLATOON Platform subpage, Energy Big Data Analytics Tools

Since it is also necessary to develop an analytical toolbox for the development of energy-specific applications, we dedicated a subpage for Energy Big Data Analytic Tools of PLATOON. These can contribute to make the existing energy system more efficient by improving processes and unleashing new services and business models.

The COSMAG-compliant reference architecture that is implemented and validated in the seven pilots. It includes innovative digital technologies focused on secure, modular, simple data access and storage and easy-to-use Energy Big Data Analytics Tools contained and usable through a marketplace, where the data sovereignty is guaranteed.

On this page, we give an overview over the analytic tool boxes implemented in the pilot projects and also present their effectiveness, efficiency and overall performance.

2.5 Pilots

The subpage “Pilots” presents the seven use cases from five countries (France, Belgium, Italy, Serbia and Spain) that will be investigated in the project. The “Pilots” category refers to every outcome of PLATOON that is publicly accessible. For the time being, the subcategories will be updated during the project’s lifetime, as soon as the first results occur.

The pilots cover the whole range of potential energy services along the energy supply chain:

1. Predictive maintenance in renewables (Wind Farm).
2. Distribution grids efficient operation and assets life extension.
3. Efficient End Use of Energy, peak avoidance and demand side response.
4. There is a fourth service so-called Optimum Energy Management in a Microgrid, which in fact considers a lot of the previous services.

“Pilots” has the following subsections:

- 1- Overview, and then 1 tab per pilot

Figure 23: PLATOON Pilots subpage, Overview

Demonstration Approach and Strategy - Overview of the PLATOON Pilots

There are 7 different pilots spread around 5 different European countries: Belgium, France, Spain, Italy and Serbia. The pilots cover the whole range of potential energy services along the energy supply chain:

1. Predictive maintenance in renewables (Wind Farm).
2. Distribution grids efficient operation and assets life extension.
3. Efficient End Use of Energy, peak avoidance and demand side response.
4. There is a fourth service so-called Optimum Energy Management in a Microgrid, which in fact considers a lot of the previous services.

The different pilots will be grouped according to the specific application field and the specific analytical tools that will be developed in each of them.

More updates will follow soon. Stay tuned!

This is an introductory section where the seven pilots, as well as the five pilot countries, are briefly presented. We included a table where we list all seven pilots, the locations, goals, application fields and functions of the analytical toolboxes, similarly as in the PLATOON GA.

2- Predictive Maintenance of Wind Farms

Figure 24: PLATOON Pilots subpage, Predictive Maintenance of Wind Farms

This section is a presentation of the Belgium pilot which focuses on the predictability of wind farm maintenance in order to increase renewable energy share within the energy market.

3- Electricity Balance and Predictive Maintenance

Figure 25: PLATOON Pilots subpage, Energy Balance and Predictive Maintenance

This category is about a pilot in Serbia that aims to improve the electricity balance of the national grid as well as making upcoming smart grid maintenance more predictable.

4- Electricity Grid Stability, Connectivity and Life Extension

Figure 26: PLATOON Pilots subpage, Energy Grid Stability and Life Extension

Here, we present a pilot from Mallorca in Spain where the PLATOON partners plan to improve the stability, life extension and flexibility of the local distribution grid as well as the connectivity by advancing energy management & control systems and tools for power grid operation.

5- Office Building: Operation Performance thanks to Physical Models and IA Algorithms

Figure 27: PLATOON Pilots subpage, Office Building: Operation Performance

This section introduces a pilot in France where the PLATOON partners strive to improve the energy operation performance of buildings with the help of physical models and AI algorithms.

6- Advanced Energy Management System and Spatial (multi-scale) Predictive Models in the Smart City

Figure 28: PLATOON Pilots subpage, Advanced Energy Management System

This Italian pilot is about the advancement of energy management systems via peak power characterisation, load forecaster and pattern recognition as well as about the creation of multi-scale predictive models for smart cities.

7- Energy Efficiency and Predictive Maintenance in the Smart Tertiary Building Hub

Figure 29: PLATOON Pilots subpage, Energy Efficiency and Predictive Maintenance

This section presents another Spanish pilot where we set the goal to increase both energy efficiency and predictive maintenance in the tertiary smart grid hub grade.

8- Energy Management of Microgrids

Figure 30: PLATOON Pilots subpage, Energy Management of Microgrids

Lastly, the last pilot section introduces another pilot in Italy where the PLATOON partners aim to find ways to optimise energy management of microgrids in order to improve energy generation and distribution as well as the end use of energy.

2.6 Resources

“Resources” has the following sections

1- Publications

Figure 31: PLATOON Resources subpage, Publications section

This category involves publications such as academic papers, journals and other sources in which the PLATOON partners are involved in.

2- Deliverables

Figure 32: PLATOON Resources subpage, Deliverables section

In this section all public WP deliverables will be uploaded such as the Del 9.1 that has been recently finalised. Hereby, we only upload completely finalised deliverables that have already been approved by the Consortium partners. These are going to be accessible for all website visitors. The “Deliverables” subpage will also display a table with all the upcoming deliverables, so that visitors can follow the project status.

3- Material

Figure 33: PLATOON Resources subpage, Materials section

In this section, the user has access to PLATOON presentations as well as posters, brochures and other project-related materials.

2.7 Network

“Network” has the sections

1- Associated Partners

Figure 34: PLATOON Network subpage, Associated Partners section

The PLATOON community will be built to engage associated partners and ambassadors that will promote the project across different countries. PLATOON has obtained Letters of Support representing a total of 7 associated parties and ambassadors across the European energy sector.

This section provides users with information on the associated PLATOON partners (the ambassadors have an own subpage that is presented further down below.).

2- Stakeholders Advisory Board

Figure 35: PLATOON Network subpage, Stakeholder Advisory Board section

At the beginning of the project, the WPL9 will establish an external and independent Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB), consisting of related high-level stakeholders, who will provide unique insights by highlighting areas where the PLATOON solution can add value. Regular meetings will be held with the SAB members during the project. Furthermore, the

SAB members will support the PLATOON project by increasing its visibility and status via dissemination activities and by indicating potential customers.

Primarily, the AB will be formed by the pilot owners not forming part of the PLATOON Consortium, i.e. the Serbian DSO EPS Electric Power Industry of Serbia Distribucija whose data are being managed by IMP, and the Italian DSO Areti who signed a Letter of Support). Other members of the Advisory Board will include very important European firms, not present in the Consortium (signed Letters of Interest at the proposal's phase), in the field of:

- Big Data and Data Governance and Sovereignty: IDSA (International Data Spaces Association) and Fraunhofer BDA, Big Data Artificial Intelligence Alliance.
- Electricity sector: GEODE (European independent distribution companies of gas and electricity), IBERDROLA (Spanish utility with businesses in the renewables, electricity distribution and commercialization).
- Energy efficiency sectors: ANESE (Spanish National ESCOs Association)

This section has the purpose to give an overview over these SAB members as well as project-related info for these and for visitors interested in becoming a member.

3- Ambassadors

Figure 36: PLATOON Network subpage, Ambassadors section

Ambassadors are experts, with a clear reputation, strong connections to companies, universities, governments and the start-up ecosystem in Europe and with a proven previous experience in Big Data and the energy sector. The Ambassador programme will be paramount to shape and give life to the PLATOON community. This programme will be key to create a crowd knowledge-based repository and a thrilling and active community. The PLATOON project objective is to activate a pool of supportive partners leveraging on the identified stakeholders to become PLATOON Ambassadors. The PLATOON community will be built to engage supportive partners and ambassadors that will promote the project across

different countries. This section serves as an overview of all engaged PLATOON ambassadors and as an info page for those that are interested to become such.

4- Tech Transfer Programme

Figure 37: PLATOON Network subpage, Tech Transfer Programme section

PLATOON's bottom-up projects generally consist of two types:

- Technology Transfer Programme 1: start-ups and SMEs developing building blocks for large scale pilots; new analytical tools for the toolbox.
- Technology Transfer Programme 2: start-ups and SMEs developing new services on top of existing technologies.

The Bottom-up projects will then become part of the Technology Transfer Programme [WP 7.4], led by TECNALIA, which will consist of 2 stages (for more info on this, see Del 9.1).

On the given subpage, we explain to the website visitors what TTPs are, who is involved in TTPs and what the purpose of those programs is.

5- Mentoring Committee

Figure 38: PLATOON Network subpage, Mentoring Committee section

The ‘Mentoring Committee’ will evaluate the bottom-up projects performance at the review milestones after both TTP stages. The evaluation criteria are the following:

- Deliverables quality. To be scored by the Technical Mentors based on the deliverables established in the IMP.
- Technical performance indicators. To be scored by the Technical Mentor based on the KPIs established in the IMP.
- Deadline Compliance. To be scored by the Technical Mentors.

This section gives a detailed insight into the members of the Mentoring Committee of the PLATOON project.

6- Accelerated SMEs and Start-ups

Figure 39: PLATOON Network subpage, Accelerated SMEs and Start-ups section

PLATOON will launch 2 open calls to engage with at least 13 SMEs and start-ups to develop new products and services. Also, we foresee to implement several specific actions in order to put the PLATOON project on the map as the initiative supporting the uptake of proposed analytical tools and the platform functionalities by start-ups, SMEs and large companies.

Therefore, we created a section completely dedicated to SMEs and start-ups where website visitors can find an overview of all of them as well as further info. FBA will collaborate with TIB and provide website content and other relevant input on the accelerated start-ups.

Specifically, FBA will:

- Provide logos, company description, and website URLs of selected SMEs in the Open Calls.
- Ask SMEs to follow PLATOON on the project’s social media accounts.
- Send an interview to SMEs and once it is answered by them, send it to TIB.

It is also important to note, that FBA will highlight the participating SMEs in the community of the project, according to task 7.5. In that way, it will look for ways to link the information

of the website to the community and vice versa, by complementing each other, avoiding repetition, and creating value for the content posted in each portal.

7- Related Projects

Figure 40: PLATOON Network subpage, Related Projects section

Since PLATOON is not the only EU project that is currently dealing with renewable energy, smart grids, and Big Data, “Related projects” gathers all relevant projects with some short information for each one. PLATOON intends to stay in close contact with these teams to assure any possible synergies and to avoid future interferences.

2.8 Ethics & Security

“Ethics & Security” has the following subsections:

1- GDPR

Figure 41: PLATOON Ethics & Security subpage, GDPR

Here you can find additional information to know how your personal data will be processed.

Cookie Declaration

This website uses cookies. We use cookies to personalise content and ads, to provide social media features and to analyse our traffic. We also share information about your use of our site with our social media, advertising and analytics partners who may combine it with other information that you've provided to them or that they've collected from your use of their services. You consent to our cookies if you continue to use our website.

Cookies are small textfiles that can be used by websites to make a user's experience more efficient.

The law states that we can store cookies on your device if they are strictly necessary for the operation of this site. For all other types of cookies we need your permission.

Which cookies and tracking software are installed?

The cookies and tracking software given below are installed on the Information Website for the Platoon European project.

These cookies and tracking software enable the Website to operate in an optimal way.

Name of cookie	Description / Objective	Storage duration
• pl_language	Used to store the user's native language	• 1 year
• pl_id • pl_ref • pl_session_pl_over_pl_hr	Used for the purposes of website audience statistics.	• 13 months • 6 months • 30 minutes
• _viewed_cookie_policy	Records the user consent for the usage of the cookies	• 1 year
• cookieslawinfo-checkbox-necessary	Records the default button state of the corresponding category	• 1 year

Here, we included a cookie declaration where we want to provide the website visitors with a detailed legal notice on cookies as well as their use.

2- Legal Notice

Figure 42: PLATOON Ethics & Security subpage, Legal Notice

Terms of Use

The newsletter subscription, including the privacy policy and legal notice, can be accessed directly on the homepage. “Legal Notice”, as a subpage of the Ethics and Security section, gives information on all the legal handling for the PLATOON partners, those who want to engage with PLATOON as well as other users that want f.e. to use the downloadable content available on the website.

After the project’s conclusion the website will be online for at least ... more years, during which the materials and results of the project will be available for project participants and for the public.

2.9 Contact

The very last PLATOON website subpage is the contact page where users have the opportunity to contact the PLATOON Communication & Dissemination leaders directly in order to ask questions, express ideas or wishes as well as give suggestions for improvement. For this, we created two contact fields – the PLATOON Communication and Dissemination Lead and Deputy Lead – with the corresponding pictures, names and emails. By clicking on the email hyperlinks a draft email pops up (depending on the email service that the visitor uses) so that the users have a chance to contact the PLATOON communication associates directly.

Figure 43: PLATOON Contact subpage

3. General Dissemination Materials

The dissemination materials were created by WP9 in order to help raise awareness of the project and maximise the impact of its dissemination activities. All the dissemination materials that were produced in the first months of the project in support of the communication & dissemination activities are presented in Chapters 3 to 5 of Del 9.2.

3.1 Project Logo

Logo and visual style

As described in Del 9.1, the complete PLATOON visual identity is designed which is centralized on a clear PLATOON logo concept and a colour pantone. The project identity aims to reinforce the project’s external image and ensure a transversal coherence between all project communication channels. Basically, it includes the project logo, documents layout and the project message. Using PLATOON’s logo beyond the limits inherent to the project and its communication is not allowed.

Project Logo

The logo has been prepared based on the criteria that it should be easily scalable, easy to reproduce, being memorable and distinctive for the viewers, and usable on a variety of media outlets. Below in Figure 44 is the official standard project logo while in Figure 45, we included some variations of our project logo as block, inline, icon only and small version coloured in standard colours, black or white.

Figure 44: PLATOON logo

Figure 45: PLATOON logo; coloured, black, white

The standard PLATOON logo is a combination of essential concepts that surround the industries involved in the project, i.e. renewable energy, data science, digitalisation, and smart homes. Hereby, the green colour symbolises climate protection, sustainability and renewable energy, whereas the purple colour stands for innovation and knowledge. There are two diamonds, whose frames are coloured in green and purple, and both figures are interlocked. To the inside of the logo, both of the diamonds are formed in a way that the interface between these two figures forms a house. Inside of the white house is a window that consists of four yellow boxes (2x2 shape). The house symbolises smart homes and the yellow window stands for energy that has been provided to the building. Inside the frames of the green and purple diamonds, there are many zeros and ones, coloured in green or purple respectively. These numbers symbolise the digitalisation trend within the energy sector.

Below the logo is the name of the project “PLATOON” written in capital letters. All letters are in a dark blue except for the two O’s that are coloured in green or purple respectively. Below “PLATOON” is the full name of the project, written in light purple, smaller size and normal letters: “Digital platform and analytic tools for energy”. The idea of PLATOON logo is that the project can be understood as an interface between the energy sector and the innovative digitalisation trend and the final goal of this project is to provide modern, smart & interconnected households, industries, buildings, among others with clean, safe, and inexpensive energy.

Project Message

The project message is a sentence that should clearly and simply state what the project is trying to achieve and which should be constantly communicated to target groups, for example by including it in projects’ promotional material such as flyers, website, press releases etc. The message agreed within the project consortium is the “PLATOON, Digital PLAtform and analytic TOOlS for eNergy”. It will be explored during the project, whether further messages will be used for communication purposes.

An easily recognisable (visual) identity of the project is essential to achieve best communication results. A Visual Identity Guide is created and made available to project partners to apply during communication and dissemination activities. It is of high importance to use these visual tools coherently.

Visual tools:

- project logo (in English)
- project molino/roll-up (in English and can be translated in national languages of the PLATOON partners)
- Templates (ppt, project newsletter, press release, scientific conference presentation, policy brief, paper, H2020 reporting/deliverable, etc.)

- general flyer/project brochure (in English and in national languages of the beneficiaries)
- project poster (in English and in national languages)
- general project website (in English)
- GA number – partners are requested to use the project GA number in all of their external communication and dissemination materials, together with
- EU emblem and the accompanying text of: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872592”.

Figure 46: EU Emblem and BDVA Logo

As indicated in the contractual information, any communication activity and result funded by the grant must display the EU emblem and include the following text to indicate that said result was generated with the assistance of financial support and that it reflects the author's view only:

- For communication activities: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872592”.*
- Disclaimer for both: *“This [insert type of result] reflects only the author’s views and the European Commission does not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”*

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have the appropriate visibility, while taking in consideration the following guidelines:

- Graphics guide to the European emblem¹
- Guide for the EU emblem²

The project partners are required to use the logos, colours of the Visual Identity Guide and the templates – some of which are listed above – developed in the framework of WP9 at all times. In order to set a common visual line for all dissemination elements, a short PLATOON visual identity manual has been released, which is communicated to the PLATOON Consortium. When the colour background does not allow good visibility of the logo, a white background or a black background version of the logo should be used according to the aesthetics of the document. The logo must be used in a black and white version in exceptional cases. Please find more detailed guidelines in D9.1.

¹ Cf. <http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

² Cf. http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/index_en.htm

3.2 Project Templates

Figure 47: PLATOON Colours, Colour Typography and Typography

Project Templates

A series of project templates were created to cover the partners’ needs. Thus, project templates suitable for deliverables, brochures, posters, stickers, presentations, newsletters, and press releases were conceived and created in order to be used by the project partners for both internal and external dissemination of the project. The templates are available in the partners’ internal repositories.

3.3 General Project Presentation Templates

PLATOON PPT templates

Figure 48: PLATOON PowerPoint template, title page

Figure 49: PLATOON PowerPoint template, content page

Figure 48 and 49 are empty PowerPoint presentation templates created by ENGIE and will be used by all partners throughout the project. The design of the slides is consistent with all the other dissemination materials that were created for presenting the project results externally or internally and distributed to all project partners and responsible WPLs respectively. Also, the project logo is adapted in all the slides of the presentation. The main purpose of this dissemination tool is for all project partners to use it for their internal and external meetings (internal project meetings, meetings with stakeholders, presentations at events etc.). The PPT template is aimed at providing exact criteria in font and font size, which makes it a well-to-use example for developing further project reports and studies. The template is available through the file sharing platform.

4. Social Media

Social media has become a very popular means of disseminating information fast across heterogeneous target groups. These channels serve on-demand access to content anytime, anywhere, on any digital device. To extend the project target audience (especially to involve the great public and not only sector experts) PLATOON is integrating these media tools strategically into the communication activities. Twitter (TW), LinkedIn (LI), and YouTube (YT) have been selected as the most appropriate social networks to promote the project achievements, news and outcomes. TIB will act as a moderator of all social media profiles, e.g. by controlling and filtering inadequate contents and monitoring the suitability and relevance of the information to be published.

4.1 Twitter Profile

Table 1: PLATOON Twitter Account

TWITTER		
	<p>Twitter @Platoon_EU Official Hashtag: #platoonh2020 #platoonproject #platoonenergy</p>	<p>Account: Use of TW will focus on broadcasting relevant PLATOON news, calls, events, and partner’s activity, in real-time if possible (i.e. live action of a PLATOON partner in an external event).</p>

Figure 50: PLATOON Twitter Homepage - Update April 2020

The @PLATOON_EU TW account (see Figure 50) is already being used for spreading the activities of the PLATOON project to the world, starting with a number of tweets about our kick-off meeting that took place from 16 to 17 January 2020 and that was hosted by ENGIE in Paris, France. The followers of this account are able to see the latest news of the project,

while the tweets of a number of related and worth-to-follow TW accounts will be also displayed via re-tweets. The background picture is changed every two months, is always energy-related and includes the PLATOON logo. In the description of the project below the background picture, PLATOON is briefly depicted in one sentence and there is a reference to the two responsible communication managers of the TW account.

Figure 51: PLATOON Twitter Analytics section

Figure 51 shows the PLATOON TW account statistics that can be seen by account admins only. Here, the communication managers can gain an insight into the performance of the project’s account, namely a 28-day-summary on the number of published Tweets, the number of Tweet impressions, the number of profile visitors, the number of project references, and the number of newly acquired followers during the given time period. This gives information on how the TW account is doing and what needs to be improved.

Below in Figure 52, we included samples of our daily tweets. Hereby, we always use visually appealing pictures under which we tag TW accounts from our partners and other related institutions. Moreover, we always include our project logo in every PLATOON-related picture used in our tweets, and we aim to make it as visible as possible as well as choose a logo

version that suits best to the corresponding picture. In our Tweet texts, we always use appealing icons that are either project-related or that are representing energy, environment, sustainability and other themes that are close to the values of PLATOON. In most Tweets, we are referring to certain websites, either our own project website or those of related European funded projects, relevant initiatives and Directorate-General (DGs) which are being promoted by the PLATOON project, such as @Energy4Europe (official twitter account of the Directorate-General for Energy), @EU_ENV (official Twitter account of the Directorate-General for Environment), @EUClimateAction (official Twitter account of the Directorate-General for Climate Action, and more as listed in D9.1, in which the communication and dissemination strategy per social media channels is fully outlined.

Figure 52: PLATOON Tweets

4.2 LinkedIn Company Page

PLATOON.eu is the official LI profile page of our project. Similarly as on TW, we use LI to share the project’s most important news as well as generic news on energy, environment, digitalisation, innovation, sustainability and other energy-related topics. Here, we also use the same background picture as on TW and we change it roughly after every 2 months. In our LI posts we include topic-related pictures which we use to tag PLATOON partners and other people that could potentially be interested in our project. Furthermore, we use hashtags, e.g. #energy, #ClimateAction, #renewables, #innovation etc. to increase the visibility of our LI posts. Also, we usually include links to either our own website or to other relevant websites where the LI visitors can get more information on PLATOON.

Table 2: PLATOON LinkedIn company page

LINKEDIN		
	<p>LinkedIn Profile:</p> <p>PLATOON.eu</p>	<p>PLATOON profile is intended as a mirror of the main updates on the PLATOON website. The most relevant contents and news of PLATOON will be posted on this profile in order to reach a wider audience.</p>

Figure 53 shows a screenshot of the LI company page from an admin’s view. Here, the admin can see the posts he or she made, a small analysis box with the corresponding data on profile visitors, new followers, impressions, and clicks on the adjusted button (all are activities during the last 30 days, similarly as on TW). Also, the admin can see the community hashtags on the right of the page as well as suggestions of contacts that could be invited to follow PLATOON.

Naturally, the admin can change the design of the LI profile, change pictures, make posts as well as like, comment, and repost the corresponding LI posts. Moreover, the admin can maintain, adapt, and change all PLATOON LI pages.

The Communication and Dissemination strategy for the LI account of the project is outlined in D9.1. In the next months, TIB will encourage the partners to enhance the visibility of the project by joining efforts in terms of posting PLATOON-related articles and blog posts on LI. The Communication and Dissemination managers will initiate these efforts aiming to serve as reference and set an example for the other consortium partners. As TIB presented at the Kick-off, all partners should be hands-on supporting and contributing to communication activities of the project, so that the envisioned impact is achieved.

Figure 53: PLATOON LinkedIn company page (admin view) - Update April 2020

Below in Figure 54, we included a screenshot of the member's view of the LI company page. The LI user can see the posts done by PLATOON as well as like, comment and repost them on his or her own LI page. Furthermore, the visitor has access to the start page, "About us" page, job vacancies page, and advertisement page. The LI user has access to the picture, documents and videos that PLATOON published, and he or she receives recommendations of pages that are either similar to PLATOON or that are energy-related. Finally, the visitor can follow the channel and see who the associates of the projects are.

Figure 54: PLATOON LinkedIn Company Page (member's view)

Further below in Figure 55, we present samples of posts that we regularly publish on our LI company page. Similarly as on TW, we always try to include many hashtags that are relevant to PLATOON as well as use visually attractive pictures that catch the viewer's attention. Also, if the posts refer to the PLATOON project we always include the PLATOON logo and make it as visible as possible.

Figure 55: PLATOON LinkedIn Posts

4.3 YouTube Account

Table 3: PLATOON YouTube Channel

YOUTUBE		
	<p>Account:</p> <p>PLATOON H2020 Project</p>	<p>Use for webinar uploads, and project related videos (e.g. interviews of the consortium partners, the accelerated start-ups/ SMEs and other related stakeholders).</p>

YT will be used to share audio-visual contents that will be shared on other media and platforms, including project-related webinars showcasing important project developments. The partners will be asked to communicate the relevant milestones of the project, as well as their participation in project events on their social media profiles.

Figure 56: PLATOON YouTube channel - About PLATOON section

The created PLATOON project channel on YT will be used for publishing videos and webinars that demonstrate and promote the activities and achievements. In order to enhance the accessibility and visibility of the videos that will be kept on this channel, links to these videos will be added on the PLATOON website (both within posts and news items as well as on the homepage itself), and disseminated through the PLATOON TW and LI accounts. More specifically, the PLATOON Project YT channel will be used as an online repository of videos that provide a brief overview of the current status and the progress made at different phases of the project's life, demonstrating the developed PLATOON platform, tools and applications; covering external activities of the project, such as interviews and training procedures, related to the PLATOON presence in events such as international conferences, meetings, workshops and so on (e.g. video captured oral presentations, where possible).

Above, Figure 56 is a snapshot of the PLATOON Project YT channel page. In the process of the time, more informative videos will be added to the channel in order to increase the number of subscribers and to disseminate the outcomes of the project.

5. Printed Materials

Press Releases

Press Releases are a major means of disseminating the project that focuses on specific achievements: milestones, developments, dissemination actions, and results. Press releases will be produced throughout the project in order to engage audiences with the project's activities and achievements.

The Press Releases are prepared by TIB, using contributions of the other Consortium partners, e.g. in the form of quotes. The press focal points nominated by each partner to contribute their ideas and/ or suggestions and the final document are also translated into

their native languages so that they can be distributed by them at national level. A document entitled “Media guidelines for press focal points” was prepared by TIB in order to provide specific guidelines on the dissemination process that the press focal points have to follow in order to achieve the proper dissemination and wider promotion of the Press Releases. The Press Releases are also uploaded on the project website, under the “News” section and they are also shared on the project’s social media accounts. Lastly, the media coverage of the Press Releases will be monitored regularly by the press focal points, making it possible to estimate the impact of the project.

5.1 Posters

The latest within six months after the start of the project, each project partner has to place at least one poster with information about the project (in A1 and A4), including the financial support from the EC (GA number), at a location visible to the public, such as the entrance area of a building. The poster has to stay visible for the whole duration of the project. The Communication and Dissemination partner (TIB) has created and distributed templates of flyers, brochures and posters to the whole PLATOON Consortium. The posters will be regularly updated and customised to reflect the latest status of the project, including specific project angles (e.g. big data tools for the energy domain, progress of the platform, open calls etc.). All updated versions will be included in the yearly editions of D9.3.

Figure 57: Updated PLATOON A1 Poster, Version 1

Figure 58: Updated PLATOON A1 Poster, Version 2A

PLATOON
Digital platform and analytic tools for energy

- The EU-funded H2020 project PLATOON aims to digitalise the energy sector, enabling thus higher levels of operational excellence with the adoption of disrupting technologies.
- PLATOON will develop a COSMAG-compliant reference architecture for big data processing for the energy sector. PLATOON will develop interoperability layer based open standards (e.g. SAREF, CIM, NGS-LD) to ensure compatibility with different platforms and legacy systems.
- PLATOON will develop IDS connectors, enabling multi-party data exchange while ensuring data governance and data sovereignty.
- PLATOON will develop a data analytics toolbox and edge computing solutions for optimized real-time energy system management in a simple way for energy domain experts.
- The project will be validated in 7 pilots in 5 countries that provide real Energy Big Data cases. PLATOON will facilitate the technology transfer into the market by a well-established tendering process via Open Calls.
- The project will reinforce the European efforts for the modernisation of the European electricity grid, as it focuses on new smart grids services through data knowledge exploitation. Moreover, PLATOON will offer access to cheaper and sustainable energy for energy consumers and maximise social welfare.
- Thus, PLATOON will contribute to increased renewable energy consumption, smart grids management, increased energy efficiency and optimised energy asset management.

KEEP IN TOUCH
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PLATOON – Partners and Pilots

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872592.

CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

Figure 59: Updated PLATOON A1 Poster, Version 2B

PLATOON
Digital platform and analytic tools for energy

- The EU-funded H2020 project PLATOON aims to digitalise the energy sector, enabling thus higher levels of operational excellence with the adoption of disrupting technologies.
- PLATOON will develop a COSMAG-compliant reference architecture for big data processing for the energy sector. PLATOON will develop interoperability layer based open standards (e.g. SAREF, CIM, NGS-LD) to ensure compatibility with different platforms and legacy systems.
- PLATOON will develop IDS connectors, enabling multi-party data exchange while ensuring data governance and data sovereignty.
- PLATOON will develop a data analytics toolbox and edge computing solutions for optimized real-time energy system management in a simple way for energy domain experts.
- The project will be validated in 7 pilots in 5 countries that provide real Energy Big Data cases. PLATOON will facilitate the technology transfer into the market by a well-established tendering process via Open Calls.
- The project will reinforce the European efforts for the modernisation of the European electricity grid, as it focuses on new smart grids services through data knowledge exploitation. Moreover, PLATOON will offer access to cheaper and sustainable energy for energy consumers and maximise social welfare.
- Thus, PLATOON will contribute to increased renewable energy consumption, smart grids management, increased energy efficiency and optimised energy asset management.

KEEP IN TOUCH
@PLATOON_EU | platoon-project.eu
PLATOON.eu | PLATOON H2020 Project

PLATOON – Partners and Pilots

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872592.

CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

The project poster provides more information on the objectives of the project, the PLATOON Consortium and an outlook on the main pillars of work and the project's expected results. It can also be handed out at conferences and other events without personal explanations. The project posters can be used as rollups aiming to create a visual identity at specific events and to mark the project area at an exhibition. Partners may also use it to promote the project locally at their offices.

5.2 Brochures

Similarly as posters and roll-ups, the production of brochures will widen the public that will be reached by the communication activities, allowing other potentially interested stakeholders and the general public to be informed about the PLATOON project.

The prepared brochure focuses on specific elements of our project (the PLATOON Consortium, target audience, events, funding calls, etc.). The brochures of the project will be accessible in electronic form so that they can be forwarded via e-mail and downloaded on the website. Furthermore, there will be printed versions to be used for conferences and live events. While preparing the brochure, special attention was given to an appealing and clear language and a friendly, light design which represents the idea of the project via nice pictures and key visuals.

Information shown in the brochure is adapted to additional formats: posters and roll-ups. These printed elements will be available for partners to be used in specific dissemination actions in events, or workshops promoting the PLATOON project (booths, etc.). At the same time, customised brochures will be prepared and updated during the project, focusing on specific project angles. For instance, dedicated brochures should reflect the project pilots separately, the developed platform and its components, the open calls etc. TIB will work closely with the technical partners and constantly update such materials which can be downloaded from the project's website, e.g. in the press section and in the specific sections as well (such as the platform section of the website).

Additional efforts will be made when the final PLATOON event approaches in terms of design of new specific promotional material for this individual event that will take place at the end of the project. Hence, the focus of these new materials will be on the final outcomes and results of the project achieved along these 3 years. We envisage producing at least the following materials for the event:

- Customized event agenda layout
- New version of the PLATOON brochure outlining the main output of the project
- Brochure adaptation to rollup format

These brochures along with the project poster will be the major printed materials to be used for dissemination purposes during conferences, workshops and other awareness events. The PLATOON Consortium partners will be offered the possibility to translate the brochure in their national languages. This will be used for the dissemination of the project outcomes and results at national level and beyond the project duration. In addition, an infographic

showcasing the output of the project will be developed and promoted in an abstractive form that can be communicated widely through online media easily.

As WPL9, TIB will be responsible for these productions. To communicate the project objectives and expected results, promotional brochures are already designed and made available to be distributed in relevant events both in printed and digital versions. The updated versions of the communication materials will be included in the yearly versions of D9.3, Dissemination and Communication Report.

Description of the first version of the brochure

To facilitate the explanation of PLATOON’s purpose and its opportunities, the first version of the brochure has been prepared resuming the project objectives and scheme. The brochure contains four pages and can be folded like a little book. It includes all logos of the 20 PLATOON Consortium partners, as well as a variation of the PLATOON logo on a violet-blue background. Below the PLATOON logo, the flag of the EU has been placed with a short text acknowledging the funding of this project by the EC and the corresponding GA number.

On the inside of the brochure, the PLATOON project is described in a few bullet points with keywords highlighted in bold. The brochure also includes information on the TW, LI, and YT page of PLATOON, as well as on the project’s website. All links are placed right next to an individually designed “Smart City” image that gives the flyer its unique character.

Figure 60: Updated PLATOON Brochure (external side)

Figure 61: Updated PLATOON Brochure (internal side)

This brochure will be distributed in conferences, workshops, and other events where consortium members will present and promote the project. Other similar materials will be elaborated to contribute to the communication of diverse PLATOON key messages, such as the results of the pilot projects.

PLATOON will provide a range of materials for non-academic audiences. Special efforts will be made to present complex ideas in an accessible and understandable manner. The PLATOON partners will be invited to translate the brochures in their national languages and redistribute via their organisations’ networks.

Besides the brochures, TIB will support the preparation of flyers for project specific actions, e.g. dissemination of open calls, webinars, workshops etc. Similarly as the brochures, the flyers will be distributed in digital or print form to all stakeholders.

5.3 Flyers

The project flyer is a one-page presentation of PLATOON, in a format that emphasises the scope and the key objectives of the project in a concise way. The layout is consistent with all the other dissemination material, including the logo, the project title, its duration and budget, the partners involved in the project, the grant agreement number, the project website, and an email for contact. Moreover, it presents the concept and the objectives of the project as it highlights some of the upcoming developments of the project. The flyer was reviewed by the project partners and will be updated regularly. It is available for the public on the project website and for the partners in their repository.

Figure 62: Updated PLATOON A4 Flyer, Version 1

PLATOON
Digital platform and analytic tools for energy

GLOBAL GOALS

- Enable the reliable, fair and secure extraction of knowledge from energy sector data.
- Foster new business models in the energy sector using digital technologies.
- Enhancing multi-party cooperation between technology providers and data owners.
- Contribute to the standards of energy management systems.
- Offer proper roles for interfaces to enable innovative business processes.
- Identify new COSMAG-compliant standards for scalable and replicable energy management solutions.

BACKGROUND & CONTEXT

- The electricity sector is shifting towards decentralisation and decarbonisation.
- The rise of renewable energy sources demands algorithms that can predict and avoid grid disturbances.
- It is necessary to leverage the data value chain to convert information into knowledge.

PLATOON - Partners and Pilots

A COSMAG-compliant reference platform with flexible capabilities:

- Interoperability**
Enabling data exchange and integrated value chains between platforms using a wide spectrum of heterogeneous data sources, formats and interfaces.
- Data Governance & Security**
Addressing digital sovereignty challenges of multiple data owners and providers for multi-party data exchange along the energy value chain via IDS-based connectors.
- Data Analytics Toolbox & Edge Computing**
Deploying technologies for data processing and analysis in batch and real-time to optimise the energy system management for the energy domain experts.

CONSORTIUM PARTNERS:

ENIGIE, tecnalia, TIB, HUBENDO, ROMA, Postelitaly, HAN DATA, VUB, GIRA, VEOLIA, FundingBox, mitsub, COM SENSUS, Gricor, UDC, Alliance, MAP, Stintplant, SAMPOL, Fraunhofer, and others.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872592

Figure 63: Updated PLATOON A4 Flyer, Version 2

5.4 Other Materials

Promotional Stickers

For dissemination purposes, stickers will be prepared and distributed within the PLATOON Consortium and beyond for dissemination purposes. The stickers will provide the following info serving the purpose to incite interest for the project and direct to the project’s website:

- the European Union’s logo and the reference EU, acknowledging the received funding and GA number,
- the name of the project
- the project’s logo and website address, along with references to its accounts on LI, TW and YT.
- Visuals highlight the project’s scope and objectives, focusing on the digitalisation of the energy sector.

Screenshots of the current versions of the stickers can be accessed here below. The stickers will further be adapted throughout the project’s duration, if necessary.

Figure 64: Updated PLATOON Sticker, Version 1

Figure 65: Updated PLATOON Sticker, Version 2

Other promotional merchandise articles

TIB will ensure that an updated media kit will be available on the project’s website. Each partner is free to design and produce promotional items suitable for distribution to stakeholders during the local dissemination events (e.g. T-shirts for conferences etc.). Nevertheless, before such items are prepared and circulated, TIB as WPL9 has to be updated about the proposed design and promotional actions first, and then review it. This is justified by the fact that TIB serves as communication consultant for the consortium and as WP9 lead at the same time. Hence, TIB has the obligation to ensure that this EU funded project is appropriately promoted and the received funding is correctly acknowledged. Such

promotional items will be featured in the yearly versions of D9.3, Dissemination and Communication Report.

6. Assessing the Impact of the COVID-19 Outbreak

The PLATOON Consortium is updated as per all the measures of the EC with relation to the ongoing EU-funded projects and this topic is discussed regularly at the level of the Steering Committee, aiming to mitigate potential negative impacts for the project. Nevertheless, it is a fact that during the first year of the project, conferences in which the PLATOON project would have been presented are being postponed for 2021. Such examples are the Hannover Messe 2020, which was initially postponed to July 2020 and then to April 2021 and the BDVA Summit in Porto. TIB, as WPL9, will facilitate this process by offering online alternatives, e.g. by proposing to the partners the organisation of webinars in which they can present the PLATOON project. This will be reported in greater detail in D9.3, due in M12.

7. Conclusion

This deliverable focuses on presenting the project's website (<http://platoon-project.eu/>) and outlining the objectives and content to be added on all menu tab sections of the website, such as "Home", "About PLATOON", "News & Events", "Platform", "Pilots", "Resources", "Network", "Ethics & Security" and "Contact" sections. At the same time the deliverable presents the current sections of each subpage, and their respective content.

Moreover D9.2 provides an overview of the promotional materials and dissemination means that will be used for making a wide spectrum of stakeholders aware of the developments, achievements and activities that take place within the context of the PLATOON project. The relevant PLATOON-related information will be made publicly available via the official project website, either in the form of posts and news items or by adding the appropriate content to the respective subpage. The project's website will act as an online repository of the project's outcomes (i.e. deliverables, publications, presentation) and developed technologies, providing access to the corresponding documents, video demonstrators and webinars. The progress made during the project's life cycle will be reflected via the PLATOON communication kit that is composed of the overall project presentation and the project leaflet. These materials, and the published newsletters, will be updated as appropriate in order to report effectively and comprehensively the project's progress. Besides the project website and the communication kit, a number of other promotional materials and dissemination means have been established in order to spread information related to the project's activities. The latter include project posters and flyers, the @PLATOON_EU TW account, the PLATOON Project YT channel and the PLATOON LI company page. Through these online communication tools the achievements and developments of PLATOON will be disseminated in wide audiences and groups of online communities, making the outcomes of the project widely visible, more accessible and further exploitable.

Along with PLATOON’s progress and development, the form and the content of the available material will evolve and, correspondingly, address the overall impact of the aforementioned tools. Therefore, it is necessary to continuously provide updates on the project’s status, along with engaging news and tweets about its activity. This will be reported in the yearly versions of D9.3.

In conclusion, online and offline communication is a continuous dynamic process that allows the PLATOON Consortium to disseminate the project, as well as their involvement, to different target groups ranging from specific stakeholders to the general public. During the next months, TIB will encourage (via regular email updates, calls to action and the organisation of monthly WP9 telcos, for which the attendance of at least one representative per partner is required), the partners to further enhance the visibility of the project by intensifying their participation in the communication and dissemination activities of the project, e.g. in terms of further promoting tweets from the project’s TW account by liking and retweeting, preparing project-related blog posts which will be disseminated via the project’s website and social media accounts, participating in webinars, further disseminating PLATOON-related articles and blog posts on LI etc. These actions and their outcomes will be reported in D9.3. The Communication and Dissemination managers will initiate these efforts aiming to serve as reference and set an example for the other PLATOON partners. As TIB presented at the Kick-off meeting, the communication of an EU funded project starts in M1 and all project partners should be hands-on supporting and contributing to communication activities of the project, so that the envisioned impact is achieved.

8. Internal Review

8.1 Internal Review 1

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes	N= no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: William Fox

Organisation: FundingBox Accelerator

Date: April 17, 2020

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	X				
... contain a license (in case of public			NA		

deliverables)?					
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?		X		Some names missing	
... contain a version table?	X				
... contain an updated table of contents?	X				
... contain a list of figures?	X				
... contain a list of tables?	X				
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	X				
... contain an Executive Summary?	X				
... contain a Conclusions section?	X				
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?	X				
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	X				
... use correct spelling and grammar?	X				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)		X		A page break between sections would be helpful to identify them.	
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)		X		No section of Annexes identified as such.	
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)	X				
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	X				

Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	X				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	X				
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	X				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	X			Although it could be more to the point in many of its contents.	
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		X			
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		X			
Are all references in the document included in the references section?		X			
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		X			
TECHNICAL RESEARCH WPs (WP2-WP5)					
Is the deliverable sufficiently innovative?			X		
Does the document present technical soundness and its methods are correctly explained?			X		
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X		

Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.			X		
VALIDATION WP (WP6)					
Does the document present technical soundness and the validation methods are correctly explained?			X		
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.			X		
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WPs (WP8 & WP9)					
Does the document present a consistent outreach and exploitation strategy?	X				
Are the methods and means correctly explained?	X				
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?			X	Has a well thought structure and is very complete and has many details.	
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X	Could miss somehow how all is connected within an overall strategy, maybe mentioning it, or linking to deliverable 9.1.	
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.			X		

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT
	In sections 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, perhaps Executive Summary	At the beginning of each section, link briefly to the overall strategy in Deliverable 9.1

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

X	Document accepted; no changes required.
	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5.

(1-Poor; 2-Fair; 3-Average; 4-Good; 5-Excellent)

Using a half point scale.

Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5
									X

8.2 Internal Review 2

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes	N= no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: Philippe Calvez

Organisation: ENGIE

Date: 27.04.2020

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	X				

... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?			NA		
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?	X				
... contain a version table?	X				
... contain an updated table of contents?	X				
... contain a list of figures?	X				
... contain a list of tables?	X				
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	X				
... contain an Executive Summary?	X				
... contain a Conclusions section?	X				
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?	X				
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	X				
... use correct spelling and grammar?	X				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes))		X		Almost under 50p	
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)		X		No Annexes (N/A if not needed)	
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)	X				
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	X				

Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	X				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	X				
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	X				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	X				
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		X			
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		X			
Are all references in the document included in the references section?		X			
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		X			
TECHNICAL RESEARCH WPs (WP2-WP5)					
Is the deliverable sufficiently innovative?			X		
Does the document present technical soundness and its methods are correctly explained?			X		
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or			X		

validation of the results, if applicable.					
VALIDATION WP (WP6)					
Does the document present technical soundness and the validation methods are correctly explained?			X		
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X		
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.			X		
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WPs (WP8 & WP9)					
Does the document present a consistent outreach and exploitation strategy?	X				
Are the methods and means correctly explained?	X				
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?			X	Cover main expectation for this type of document and structured clearly the content	
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?			X	Lack of innovative ways to support this communication. Focus on the most powerful and well-known tools and channels	
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.			X	Rely on KPI that are normally used	

				for this type of Communication channels. (number of followers, etc...)	
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SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

X	Document accepted; no changes required.
	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5.

(1-Poor; 2-Fair; 3-Average; 4-Good; 5-Excellent)

Using a half point scale.

Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5
									X

9. References

[1] H2020 Programme, AGA – Annotated Model Grant Agreement³

[2] Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants, Version 1.0 25 September 2014⁴

[3] H2020 Programme, Guidance, Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects, EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, Version 1.1

³ Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf#page=277

⁴ Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf
<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLvpwljZTs-Lhe0wu6uy8gr7JFfmv8EZuH>

07 January 2020⁵

[4] Making the Most of Your H2020 Project, Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation, European IPR Helpdesk⁶

[5] Graphics guide to the European emblem, Publications Office of the European Union⁷

[6] ARTICLE 38.1 — Communication activities by beneficiaries⁸

[7] European IP Helpdesk⁹

⁵ Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

⁶ Cf. https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E_0.pdf

⁷ Cf. <http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

⁸ Cf. https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders/opportunities/content/article-381-%E2%80%94-communication-activities-beneficiaries_en

⁹ Cf. www.iprhelpdesk.eu